

Description of the experiment for the detection of the hypothetical presence of the Immaterial Fluid constituting the spacetime

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Abstract

We have successfully conducted an experiment that, if confirmed, would be a sufficient condition to demonstrate the presence of a possible fluid medium constituting spacetime. At the moment, we are waiting to repeat it under controlled conditions. In this article, we describe the experiment and the underlying theory. We publish it with documentary value and as a stimulus for further investigations.

Introduction

Each of the following considerations refers to the theory exposed in Ref. 1,2,3. We described the structure of a fluid medium that has the same behavior of the physical vacuum^{1 2 3}. We have called it Immaterial Fluid (Note A). In the hypothesis that the Immaterial Fluid constitutes the spacetime, in analogy with superfluids in similar theories, it would permeate all of space, either the isolated regions and the interiors of atoms, between the constituent particles^{9 10 11 12}. The Immaterial Fluid is made up of Immaterial Atoms bosons, IAs^{1 2 3}. They are present in a discrete quantity, constituting a three-dimensional grid¹. Adjacent IAs present alternated spin $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$ ^{1 3}. The variables describing the state of the individual IA vary in a continuous way^{1 3}. These bosons are given by the overlap of electron and positron in a virtual state¹. That is, two opposite pure leptonic charges, characterized by their own spin and magnetic dipole¹³. In a stable, unperturbed equilibrium, IAs' fields would be mutually null^{1 2 3} (Note B). In a fully symmetric state where all fields vanish and no reference interaction exists, mass would not be an observable quantity. It would still exist as a theoretical parameter, but it would not manifest dynamically^{14 15 16}. Based on the energetic and gravitational conditions around them, IAs undergo large spacetime distortions, consistent with relativistic curvature effects^{1 3}. We have physically described how theoretically mass, gravity^{1 2}, and time³ emerge from the Immaterial Fluid, how the transmission of waves occurs through IAs³, how virtual particles appear and disappear due to IAs oscillation during waves transmission^{1 2 3},

and the mechanism through which waves' speed always remains constant and equal to that of light³. Based on the characteristics of the Immaterial Fluid, we refuted the interpretations of the Michelson-Morley experiment³. That is, the fact that the speed of the light beams remained constant is in agreement with the existence of a superfluid that has the characteristics of the Immaterial Fluid made up of IAs³.

Methods

The higher the energy status of IAs, the smaller their characteristic dimensions^{1 3}. The momentum of the wave distorts the size of the IAs on which the wave transits³. In the Michelson-Morley experiment the two final beams arrive parallel on the screen⁴. The Immaterial Fluid through which beams of light propagate has such characteristics³ that they always have the same speed³. Hence the invariance of the interference in the Michelson-Morley experiment³. If beams travel parallel to each other, they also have the same frequency³. Based on the characteristics of the Immaterial Fluid, we have designed and realized the device to detect its possible presence. A beam of light against the "ether wind" would have a smaller momentum and therefore a longer wavelength than in the condition with "ether wind" in favour^{4 5}. And vice versa. IAs bosons have a similar behaviour, that is, synthetically, the less energy or momentum they possess the larger they are^{1 3}. This happens because the wave is the propagation of energy through IAs^{1 3}. This propagation occurs by transmitting polarization between IAs³. Each IA diffuses its own polarization to the adjacent one and so on³. The increase of energy due to the wave on the IAs, reduces their characteristic dimensions³, and vice versa. The time delay of the propagation of the polarization between adjacent IAs is that due to the speed of light³.

The experiment - sufficient but not necessary to highlight the presence of the Immaterial Fluid - could consist of colliding two laser beams on a screen. The beams should form an angle of almost 180° between them. The cross-section of the beam should be non-point-like, such as a segment or a circle. The lasers are then positioned so that the figures projected on the screen intersect. A line at each segment, or the outline of the intersecting figure must be drawn. Finally, the entire device is rotated, keeping the relative positions of all the components fixed. According to modern physics, the described experiment will not show any observable physical changes^{5 6 7 8}. If a small displacement of the projected beams with respect to the traces left on the screen in the previous configuration will be observed, or an alteration of the current figures in the area of the overlapping beams, it would be therefore sufficient to highlight the presence of the Immaterial Fluid.

Results

On 30th September 2024 we built a device to detect the possible presence of the Immaterial Fluid. In the same day, we performed the experiment 5 times, with positive results. We filmed it 3 times, we disassembled the equipment, we archived the videos (Note C). The device used was equipped with two laser beams. The characteristics of the beams used are summarized in Fig. 1 and 2. Fig. 3 shows the device. It consisted of a rotating platform about 3m long, with a screen in the centre. On the two sides of the screen, at a distance of about 1.5 m, there were two laser projectors with a very inclined incidence compared to the surface of the screen, almost parallel to it. The two laser beams projected two oblique segments on the screen, intersecting each other. With a marker we have drawn a line on the screen, coinciding with the projection of each laser segment (Fig. 4). We have placed the attention on that of Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Parameters of the laser beam whose deviation is been observed

Figure 2 Parameters of the laser beam which has not been the subject of in-depth observations

Figure 3 Photo of the detector device for the Immaterial Fluid medium. The rotating platform, the screen in the centre, and the two laser projectors on the sides are visible. The rays are projected almost parallel to the screen surface and trace two inclined segments on it

At this point, using the platform, we rotated the entire device by 90°. Each constituent part kept its position unchanged with respect to the platform, but the projection of the laser segment no longer fell on the line traced with the marker (Fig. 5). A

displacement also occurred in other configurations, but when returning to the initial one, the laser light projected its segment again onto the line initially drawn with the marker.

The explanation would be that, as already stated, in a more or less favorable direction with the "ether wind", waves have a specific momentum and, as a consequence, a specific wavelength^{4 5}. The characteristic dimensions of the IAs undergo distortions due to the transit of the waves³. Rotating the device, varies the direction of the laser beam in respect to the "ether wind". Therefore, the momentum of the beam varies⁴ and consequently the characteristic dimensions of the IAs through which the waves propagate³. As a consequence, the trajectory of the laser beam, in the rotated configuration, no longer falls on the line drawn with the marker, but undergoes a deviation.

Figure 4 Situation at the initial configuration. At the top right it is possible to see the black line into the laser projection

Figure 5 Situation after a rotation of about 90°. On the right it is possible to see that now the black line is outside the laser projection

Conclusions

We designed this experiment starting from the characteristics of the Immaterial Fluid^{1 2 3}. The results obtained from the experiment are totally in line with what was assumed before it was carried out. However, it was not technically possible to exclude with absolute certainty the influence of external factors or possible systematic errors. Still for technical reasons, it was not even possible to perform the experiment on multiple dates or separate locations. So, this article is being published with documentary value and as a stimulus for further investigations, but it cannot be considered scientifically founded. Given the relative simplicity of the experimental apparatus, it could be equally easy to reproduce the same experiment under controlled conditions, by appropriately modulating the physical parameters involved (Note D). If this experiment will be confirmed, it could represent a sufficient condition to highlight the presence of the Immaterial Fluid.

Notes

A The immaterial fluid can be identified with what was once hypothesized as "ether". We think it is appropriate to call it Immaterial Fluid because, unlike what happened for the ether, we have now described its structure and behavior in a manner consistent with the experimental results^{1 2 3}. We believe that using the word "ether" would risk proving misleading or referring to cultural settings that are probably inappropriate here.

B The stable, unperturbed equilibrium is a hypothetical condition^{1 2 3}. In the considered region of Immaterial Fluid, there would not be gravitational or electromagnetic fields, no background radiation, no form of quantum fluctuations.

C Figures 3,4,5 show three frames of one of these videos.

D It could be theoretically possible to find the same result of the experiment even using a smaller device, perhaps equipped with a lens to better view the area of deviation between the incident rays on the screen and the drawn line. Theoretically, even less powerful laser beams could be sufficient to highlight the results. It would be preferable if they are rotatable around their projection axes, adjustable in frequency, geometry of the projections, intensity and other parameters if necessary. We consider it useful to mount the laser projector on a rod with adjustable position relative to the screen, variable in the radial coordinate and in the two angular ones.

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